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Impact of Water-rationing on Zimbabwe's High Density Suburbs: A Case of Harare (Capital City)

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Impact of Water-rationing on Zimbabwe's High Density Suburbs: A Case of Harare (Capital City)

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ABSTRACT

Water-cuts were introduced in the City of Harare, the intention was to control (actually reduce) water consumption. A lot of controversy resulted from this move. People questioned its effectiveness against the health risks imposed on the residents. The gist of this paper is the cost-effectiveness of water-cuts. Findings show that more woes came from water-cuts. For instance, bills soared, the environment became very dirty and personal hygiene fell to its nadir. Recommendations were made to address the problem of water shortages without creating worse problems for the residents concerned.

Key Words: Water-Rationing; Shedding; Conservation; Consumption; Hygiene; Household; Environment.

1. BACKGROUND

Safe drinking water is a basic necessity for good health. Unsafe drinking water can be a significant carrier of diseases such as cholera, typhoid and schistosomiasis. Inadequate disposal of human excreta and personal hygiene is associated with a range of diseases which include diarrhea. The Millennium Development Goal number 7C is aimed at reducing by half, between 1990 and 2015, the proportion of people without sustainable access to safe drinking water and basic sanitation. Having reached the end of year 2015, it becomes imperative to assess the extent to which the goal was attained. While it is true that urban populations have access to treated water, it cannot be denied that their rural counterparts do not have to put up with hours and hours of water cuts.

The Harare City Council, in collaboration with Zimbabwe National Water Authority (ZINWA) began water shedding so as to curb the use of water in the high density suburbs. With swelling population figures due to the rural-to-urban migration, water consumption had to be controlled. Measures had to be taken to ensure that it lasted until the next rainy season. Families went for many hours without water. Open spaces were used as toilets (defecation); used sanitary pads and used pampers/diapers were strewn all over. The availability and accessibility of clean drinking water for domestic use plays a significant role in the uplifting of general standard of living of people. Government policy stipulates that all planned urban residential areas should have reticulated water supply connected to each and every stand. All sanitary facilities should be water-borne.

1.1 Statement of the problem

Water-shedding exposes residents to health hazards and damages the environment.

1.2 Objectives

- To describe the factors leading to water-shedding.
- To explore the aspects of people's livelihoods, which are most affected by water shedding.
- To investigate the residents' coping strategies in the face of water cuts.
- To evaluate the effects of water shedding, burst water pipes and sewer pipes on the health of residents and the environment.
- Examine other water conservation strategies (other than water shedding), that the local authorities and residents can employ without compromising health or damaging the environment.

1.3 Significance of the Study

This study adds to the knowledge on the risks of water cuts. It enlightens readers about less risky ways of conserving water and also stimulates other stakeholders to conduct further studies in this field.

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1.4 Delimitation

The study covered Glen Norah, Glen View and Budiriro high density suburbs of Harare were studied. Low density residential areas were not included because most of them had bore-holes and other sources of water.

1.5 Limitations

In dealing with open defecation, participants had personal inhibits and so not all information was released. The return of questionnaires remained around 60% until the researchers made a follow-up. Participants could have worked more smoothly with face-to-face interviews, which required more time form the researcher. The researchers therefore made use of weekends and time after work to complete the scheduled interviews successfully.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Public Service Report, (2006) says safe water includes piped water (inside or outside house); communal tap and protected borehole/well. It explains that the provision of safe water for domestic purposes is one of the key priorities in the improvements of peoples' standards of living. The United Nations Millennium Development Goal 7 aimed at halving the proportions of people without sustainable access to drinking water by 2015. The provision of clean water minimizes the contracting of water-borne diseases and results in healthier communities. In the long run, fewer resources are spent on health.

About water supply system(s) serving Harare, Nhapi, (2009) says there is limited human capacity and financial capacity in urban centers, to provide efficient water services. Since the late 1980's, most urban centers in Zimbabwe experienced water challenges due to poor rainfall, insufficient qualified water challenges due to poor rainfall, insufficient qualified resources-personnel; population growth, aging infrastructure and corruption, (Rondinelli 1991; Chatora, Taylor and Hoe Venaars, (1995), Mangizvo and Kapungu, (2010) point out that the rapid growth of urban populations contributes to increase in the demand for fresh domestic water in the urban areas. Zimbabwe's urbanization rates, estimated to be 4,6%, Chatiza and Mlalazi, (2009) exert too much pressure on the water which is a finite and vulnerable resource. Schutte, (1996) and the UNDP Report, (2006) both stress the need for making water available to residents. The literature rightfully emphasizes the importance of clean water but no attention is paid to the water-cuts and the ensuing challenges.

Global Water Shortages

The International Association of Hydrologists, cited in Fontein, (2008) revealed that ground water is the world's most extracted raw material. It is also possible that international and civil wars will be fought over water, not oil De Villiers, (1998). In his study of year 2000, Rakodi discovered that water shortages In Harare were not as bad as they were in Bulawayo (i.e. the second largest city in Zimbabwe). However, there were more families per household in Harare and this is what exacerbated the problem.

According to the United Nations Water Report, (2006), scientific and technical knowledge for the prevention and management of water scarcity are available. Water resource managers were found struggling to balance supply and demand for water in the face of uncertainties brought about by the unpredictability of weather conditions (Ivey et.al.2004). He also says political and institutional restructuring had resulted in the responsibility shifting from the state to local authorities and agencies. Providing good-quality drinking water regularly is a challenge internationally (Ammons, 2001). Since the reviewed literature makes it clear that provision of fresh water is a challenge, this study was motivated to examine the implications of water cuts to residents.

In the cities studied by Rakodi, (2000), it was found that during interruptions, the flow of air through pipes was registered and this resulted in higher meter readings. Attention was paid to distorted meter readings, physical damage to the water system as reported by water engineers and lowered pressure. Neither enough attention nor concern was directed towards health and the environment. This is why this study was conducted, Published studies had not yet focused on the immediate and user friendly methods of addressing the problem of water shortage(s).

3. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

This study employed the descriptive survey to handle the “What”, “How”, “Where”, “Why” and “When” type(s) of research questions, Hair et.al, (2008). Questionnaires and face-to-face interviews were used to compliment secondary data. Cooper and Schindler, (2003) show the merits of using questionnaires. While Frankel and Warren, (1996) are in favour of interviews. Key informant face-to-face interviews had to be conducted in order to gather qualitative data.

Sampling and Sample Size

Random sampling was used in the selected high density areas. A family was counted as one unit or one participant. So household-structured questionnaires were designed and this was the major tool for collection of quantitative data.

Table 1: Sample for This Study

Residential Area	Number Of Participants
Glen Norah	50
Glen View	50
Budiriro	50
Total	150

A pilot study was conducted and it benefited this study because it revealed errors, prejudice and ambiguities. These weaknesses were attended to, in order to improve the data collection exercise and ensure that the data collected were accurate. However, the return rate of questionnaires was below 60% and this made the researcher adjust the schedule of data collection. It became necessary to increase the number of face-to-face interviews.

4. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Data were presented in the form of simple tables, bar-graphs and descriptions. The implications of quantitative findings were briefly explained.

It was discovered that water-shedding was not an option. Without control of consumption, residents would at some time have no water at all. With increasing urban populations, climate change and unpaid water-bills, it was found imperative to introduce water-cuts. There were about 3 people per room and this raised levels of water consumption. Each house had an average of three tenants, people occupying the house which they do not own.

Table 2: Duration of Water Shedding

Period	Frequency	Percentage (%)
12-24hours	30	20
24-48hours	61	40.6
48-72hours	42	28
72hours	7	4.6
	150	100

The majority of participants (61%) described the longest duration of water-cuts to be 48hours, which is not easy to bear with. Very few participants experienced water shedding for up to three consecutive days (72hours).

Personal Hygiene and Health Issues

Having access to both an improved drinking water source and an improved sanitation facility could be said to bring the largest public health benefits to a household, Wolf, *et al*, (2014). This study found that for urban dwellers, the major challenge is that there are alternative sanitation facilities to be used during periods of water cuts. Wealth quintiles are of little significance because even the upper echelons of the socio- economic ladder are hard hit by water cuts.

Safe disposal of a child's faeces is when a child uses a toilet or when a child's stool is rinsed or deposited into a toilet or latrine. Disposal diapers are thrown into ditches, buried or left in the open. All these are poor practices of disposing children's waste. Another area that has been covered extensively by the literature review is that of hand washing. Cairncross and Valdmanis, (2006) posit that hand washing with water and soap is the most cost effective health intervention to reduce the incidence of both diarrhea and pneumonia. They argue that it is most effective when done after visiting the toilet or changing a baby's diaper, before eating or handling food. However, it was found that despite being aware of correct hand washing behavior, urban dwellers could not do much without water. Many practices were known but not done due to water cuts.

Personal hygiene was a concern for everybody as bathing and washing of hands, were examples of wastage of water. For women, the water-cuts were strongly felt as they had a hard time during menstruation, baby-nursing and execution of general household chores. They could not enjoy the recommended regular baths to maintain their cleanliness and freshness. The disposal of sanitary pads became a night-mare. Even the mothers whose babies were using napkins which needed to be washed on a daily basis, had a solid waste as there was no water for flushing the toilets. Some participants expressed fear that their toddlers might drown in the containers which they used to store water inside their houses. Family members expressed discontent over the fact that their vegetables had dried up. They then had to look for cash to buy the vegetables which they so much needed for their meals. The environment was said to be very dirty as most residents used the open space(s) or business to defecate. Residents were unhappy, that even when they got their water back, it was always contained and somehow "brownish in color". An interview with a ZINWA Operations Engineer confirmed that burst pipes and rust caused water to be contaminated what water supplies were restored. A lot of water saving-strategies had been adopted by most households. During water cuts, several alternative sources of water were resorted to (see Fig1 below)

Figure 1: Alternative Sources of Water during Water-Cuts

From the alternative sources shown on the pie-chart, chances of water-borne diseases were found to be extremely high. Unbearable odors were coming from the nearest bushes and even from inside the houses. Hoarding of water made water-cuts ineffective. The consumption of water actually went-up instead of being reduced.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusions

- Participants' personal hygiene was negatively affected. They could not bath as often as necessary.
- The surrounding environment was heavily polluted by solid human waste; worsened by bursting of sewer pipes which was common place.
- Some residents had learnt to restrict the use of piped, treated water to drinking and cooking.
- On average, water charges were rather too high and most families owed a lot of money (in the form of unpaid bills) to Harare City Council.
- Not enough was known about water conservation, except recycling water, closing water taps and fixing damaged taps.
- Harare needs construction of additional dams to cater for growth in water demands.

5.2 Recommendations

- City-wide campaigns through the media would help increase Harare residents' awareness of the need to cut water and conserve it.
- Harare City Council could alleviate the problem by drilling more bore-holes as trailed water tanks are not reliable alternative sources of water.
- In this endeavor, ZINWA experts should be actively involved to ensure that underground water is harvested beyond acceptable volumes
- Advocate for roof top water harvesting through gutters into raised water tanks for domestic uses.
- It is strongly recommended that a financing strategy is developed for replacing aging infrastructure.
- There is also need to update tariff policy in order to improve financial viability and address needs of the poor.
- New mitigation strategies that make Urban Water Supply system more efficient and effective.
- New pipes are needed to replace old, worn out pipes which burst time and again.
- More dams should be constructed. It is imperative to solicit the support and involvement of private stakeholders in the service management of urban water

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